

STUDY OF NON-DESTRUCTIVE MEASUREMENT APPROACH OF RESIDUAL STRESS ON FRP LAMINATE BASED ON THERMAL EXPANSION

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we focused on the effects of residual stress on linear expansion coefficient of bulky materials in order to measure residual stress that occurred to structure in non-destructive manner. Residual stress can cause defects such as cracking, and extreme drop of mechanical properties. Thus it is important to measure residual stress, especially in bulky materials. If a material containing residual stress expanded under heating condition, the amount of thermal expansion should be affected by the amount of residual stress. Therefore, we supposed that the linear expansion coefficient is one of the index of residual stress inside materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have been attracted attentions as a material for large-scale structures such as aircraft and ship. CFRP is formed of resin as base material and fiber. CFRP has excellent specific strength and elastic modulus, and ratio strength is 4-5 times of the steel [1]. Large-scale CFRP structures are normally made by an autoclave. In a molding process of FRP, curing of resin occurred from outside of material, then gradually inside resin is cured along with heat transfer. At this stage, residual stress is caused by the difference of linear expansion coefficient and shrinkage between resin and fiber. Residual stress causes defects such as cracking, and extreme drop of mechanical properties [2]. Because residual stress has size effect, larger structure is, then larger residual stress becomes.

Measurement methods of residual stress can be classified into two categories according to destructive or non-destructive [2]. Example of the destructive measurement methods of residual stress are ones using measurement of strain released by Hole-Drilling or grinding [3,4]. These methods are limited to measure the specimen, and cannot use for structural material by destruction. The non-destructive measurement methods are the ones using X-ray diffraction and neutron diffraction [3]. These methods are limited to measure the very local residual stress less than micrometric unit [5]. Neutron diffraction method can measure deep part than measurement of X-ray diffraction. Even if it is

steel, the measurement can 50mm depth approximately now. However, the CFRP used as large structural is difficult measurement become the size of the metric unit [6,7]. Furthermore, Raman spectrum attracted attentions as measurement method for residual stress because this method is possible relatively deep part of materials. But this method is also limited to measure the very local residual stress less than micrometric unit [8,9]. Thus, the method for measurement of non-destructive which can measure residual stress occurring the structure body is desirable.

In this study, we focused on the effects of residual stress on linear expansion coefficient of bulky materials. If a material containing residual stress expanded under heating condition, the amount of thermal expansion should be affected as a function of the amount of residual stress. Therefore, we thought that the linear expansion coefficient is one of the index of residual stress inside materials. Figure 1 shows a schematic illustration of correlation between thermal expansion and residual stress.

Figure 1: A schematic illustration of correlation between thermal expansion and residual stress.

As shown in the center of Figure 1, a material without residual stress can expand freely according to linear expansion coefficient. On the other hand, as shown in right hand of Figure 1, thermal expansion behavior should be restricted by internal residual stress if the material contained residual stress. Therefore the apparent thermal expansion should be changed by residual stress. If the correlation between the apparent thermal expansion measured by external strain and the internal residual stress, the residual stress could be estimated or calculated from the external strain of bulky material.

In this study, we made FRP laminates with stacking sequence in block-manner, in order to intentionally cause residual stress. Produced residual stress was firstly estimated by finite element analysis (FEM). Then the difference in linear expansion coefficient of materials with or without residual stress was measured experimentally by a thermal mechanical analyser (TMA). Residual stress estimated by numerical simulation was verified by the existing destructive measurement methods such as Hole-Drilling. Through this process, or iteration process, we tried to obtain the correlation between residual stress and “apparent” thermal expansion behavior of materials.

2 SAMPLE

The specimen was made with carbon fiber / epoxy prepregs (Toray Industries, Inc., T800SC/#2592). Laminates were molded by an autoclave (A-3412, Ashida MFG. Co., Ltd.). Two types of laminate were prepared; one was cross-ply laminate with stacking sequence of $[(0/90)_6/0/90/0/(90/0)_6]$, and the other was one with $[0_7/90_{13}/0_7]$. The former laminate was made as a reference material, and the latter was a laminate including residual stress. Here, because the total number of layers stacked along each direction was same in each laminate, mechanical properties, at least in in-plane direction, were ideally equivalent.

3 ANALYSIS

Residual stress intentionally applied by changing the orientating angle was estimated theoretically by FEM. Pre-post software was MSC.Mantat 2013.1.0 for modering and calculation was conducted by MSC.Marc 2013.1.0 as a commercialized nonlinear finite element analysis program produced by MSC Software company.

3.1 ANALYSIS CONDITION

We made a one-eighth symmetry border model of the specimen. Model size is 5mm×5mm×1.62mm which the specimen for measurement of residual stress. Each model's boundary condition with a fiber direction, a fiber right angle direction, a thickness direction. And boundary condition of temperature is all elements decrease of -105°C. Figure 2 shows boundary condition of FEM model. And table 1 shows material properties of analysis model. The thermal expansion coefficients obtained by experimental measurement were applied to the models in order to cause models residual stress based on the thermal expansion. Thermal decrease of -105°C was applied to cause models as a boundary condition, which was the gap between room temperature and molding temperature of 130 °C. In addition to the thermal expansion, cure shrinkage of matrix resin was also considered in our models. The rate of cure shrinkage was estimated by the unit cell model of composite, in which the strain of matrix based on a literature [10] was applied.

Figure 2: Boundary condition of FEM model.

Table 1: Material properties used in FEM models.

Material property for FEM			
Fiber elastic modulus	E_f	[GPa]	294
Fiber Poisson's ratio	ν_f	-	0.2
Matrix elastic modulus	E_m	[GPa]	3.5
Matrix Poisson's ratio	ν_m	-	0.38
Volume fraction of fiber	V_f	-	0.6
Elastic modulus	E_1	[GPa]	177.8
	$E_2=E_3$	[GPa]	13.4
	$\nu_{12} (= \nu_{13})$	-	0.272
Poisson's ratio	$\nu_{23} (= \nu_{32})$	-	0.595
	$\nu_{31} (= \nu_{21})$	-	0.021
	$G_{12} (= G_{31})$	[GPa]	4.856
Shear modulus	G_{23}	[GPa]	4.201
	α_T	[1/°C]	48.65×10^{-6}
Linear expansion coefficient	α_L	[1/°C]	-0.405×10^{-6}

3.2 ANALYSIS RESULT

Figure 3 and 4 show analysis result of cross ply laminate and block laminate respectively. Values in the result show the Maximum principal stress. The closer the color of part becomes yellow, the higher the stress becomes. Table 2 shows the values of stress at the center of each laminate. Here, the number “1” indicates the fiber direction, “2” is the perpendicular direction to the fiber, and “3” shows the through-the-thickness direction of laminate.

Figure 3: Maximum principal stress distribution of cross ply stacking(σ_y).

Figure 4: Maximum principal stress distribution of block stacking(σ_y).

Table 2: Maximum principal stress.

Laminate condition		σ_x	σ_y
cross ply	[MPa]	59.96	69.34
block	[MPa]	4.523	184.6

From these results, it was found that the stress at the center of block-manner stacked laminate was higher than that of cross-ply one. The difference of stress 2 models means the residual stress caused by the difference of stacking sequence. Here, becomes stress relaxation was found in both 2 models at the

range of 2mm from the edge, it is necessary that these regions should be avoided in an experimental measurement of residual stress.

4 MEASUREMENT OF THERMAL EXPANSION WITH THERMAL MECHANICAL ANALYZER (TMA)

In order to verify the residual stress estimated by using FEM, experimental measurement was conducted through the hole-drilling method. Specimens were cut along the direction and the perpendicular direction of fiber, respectively. Dimension of each specimen was as follows; 3mm in thickness, 9mm in width and 20mm in length.

4.1 MEASUREMENT RESULT

The effect of stacking sequence of laminate on a coefficient of thermal expansion was evaluated by the thermal mechanical analyzer (TMA 8310, Rigaku, Co.). Because it is difficult to measure the temperature beyond glass-transition point, the range of measurement temperature was limited from room temperature to 80°C. Heating rate was 10°C/min., and specimen was annealed at 80°C for 5min. Figure 5 shows the thermal expansion-time diagram. Here, “cross” and “block” represent thermal expansion measured in cross-ply laminate and block-manner stacked laminate. In addition, “L” represents the thermal expansion measured in the specimen cut along the fiber direction, and “T” represents that measured along the perpendicular direction.

Figure 5: Comparison of thermal expansion between cross-ply and block-manner stacked CFRP laminate.

In all cases, thermal expansion shows linear correlation with temperature in the range measured. Thus, linear thermal expansion coefficient was obtained in the range of temperature between 30°C and 50°C.

Linear expansion coefficient was calculated by the following equation.

$$\alpha = \Delta L / (L \times \Delta T) \quad (1)$$

ΔL : Extension, L: Initial length,

ΔT : Temperature change, α : Linear expansion coefficient

Figure 6: Linear expansion coefficient.

Table 3: Linear expansion coefficient.

		Linear expansion coefficient [1/°C]
cross-ply	T	1.35E-06
	L	1.57E-06
block	T	3.00E-06
	L	4.01E-06

Figure 6 and Table 3 shows linear expansion coefficient calculated by equation (1). As shown in Figure 6, block-manner stacked laminate showed higher linear expansion coefficients than cross-ply laminate in both L and T directions. Mechanical property in in-plane direction, including thermal expansion coefficient, are theoretically same between these L and T samples because the number of layers stacked along each direction was same in both specimens. Thus, it is supposed that the difference of thermal expansion coefficient between these samples was caused by generation of residual stress.

5 EXPERIMENTAL MEASUREMENT OF RESIDUAL STRESS BY HOLE-DRILLING

In order to verify of residual stress estimated by FEM, we conducted experimental measurement of residual stress in CFRP laminate by using hole-drilling method.

CFRP laminates were molded as mentioned in 2. Specimens for measurement of thermal expansion coefficient were cut from laminates in dimension of each specimen was as follows; 3mm in thickness, 120mm in width and 170mm in length.

5.1 MEASUREMENT RESULT

Empirical measurement of residual stress was conducted by the hole-drilling method defined by ASTM E837-08. In this method, variation of strains around a hole was monitored by roset-type strain gauge (FRAS-2-11, Tokyo Sokki Kenkyujo Co., Ltd.) while a hole was formed by a milling machine (Matsuura Machinery Corporation, MC-800VF) with a 2mm-diameter end mill. The depth of a hole formed in a single step was 0.05mm, and drilling process was iterated 15 times. Strain variation was monitored and recorded by a self-mode program using LabVIEW 2014 (National Instruments, Ver.14.0 LabVIEW professional development system).

Figure 7: Results of residual stress measurement.

Figure 7 (a) and (b) show measurement results of residual stresses in cross-ply and block-manner stacked laminates, respectively. Here, mean values of residual stress, summarized in Table 3, were defined in a range from 0.3 to 0.6mm in depth of holes.

Table 3: Mean values of residual stress.

		σ_x	σ_y
cross-ply	[MPa]	59.96	69.34
block	[MPa]	4.523	184.6

In the cross-ply laminate, stresses measured in both L and T directions (denoted as σ_x and σ_y in Fig. 6) were almost same. From this result, it is obvious that equivalent in-plane stresses were induced in the cross-ply laminate. On the other hand, distinct difference of stresses was confirmed between L and T directions in the block-manner stacked laminate, in which especially the stress in T (denoted as σ_y) was very high. Thus, it was clear that significant amount of residual stress was induced by the stacking sequence of CFRP laminate.

6 CORRELATION BETWEEN RESIDUAL STRESS AND LINEAR EXPANSION COEFFICIENT

Figure 8 shows a diagram of the correlation between residual stress and linear expansion coefficient in cross-ply and block-manner stacked laminates. From this result, it is clear there is strong linear relationship between residual stress and linear expansion coefficient. Thus, it is expected that the measurement of thermal expansion behavior of target structural material leads estimation of internal and invisible residual stress. In our future work, we will clarify the correlation between exterior thermal expansion and residual stress.

Figure 8: Relationship of linear expansion coefficient and residual stress.

7 CONCLUSION

In this study, we focused on the correlation between thermal expansion behavior and residual stress in CFRP laminates. We intentionally induced residual stress by arranging stacking sequence of laminates. Thermal linear expansion coefficient was measured by thermal mechanical analyzer. Residual stress was estimated by finite element analysis at first, then it was verified by experimental measurement results obtained by hole-drilling method. It is clear there is strong linear relationship between residual stress and linear expansion coefficient. Thus, it is expected that the measurement of thermal expansion behavior of target structural material leads estimation of internal and invisible residual stress. In our future work, we will clarify the correlation between exterior thermal expansion and residual stress.

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